

A sampling and conditioning particle system for solid particle measurements down to 10 nm

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Abstract

The measurement of vehicle particle number emissions and, therefore, regulation, necessitates a rigorous sampling and conditioning technology able to deliver solid emitted particles with minimum particle losses. European legislation follows a solid particle number measurement method with cutoff size at 23 nm proposed by the Particle Measurement Programme (PMP). Accordingly, the raw exhaust is sampled with constant volume, subsequently passes through a volatile particle remover (VPR), and finally is measured with a particle counter. Lowering the 23 nm cutoff size with current VPR technologies introduces measurement uncertainties mainly due to the high particle losses and possible creation of artefacts.

This study describes the development and evaluation of a sampling and conditioning particle system, the SCPS, specially designed for sub-23 nm solid particles measurement. The dilution process is achieved in two stages; the primary dilution is done with a porous tube while the secondary with an ejector diluter that also acts as a pump for the sampling flow. The SCPS offers flexibility in terms of dilution ratio (DR) which is real-time calculated with an algorithm based on a differential pressure measurement across an orifice. Between the two dilution stages, a catalytic stripper removes volatile material with high efficiency. The SCPS evaluation includes the DR calculation algorithm testing, the stability of DR during transient engine conditions, the volatile particle removal efficiency with tetracontane particles, the solid particle penetration efficiency with polydisperse CAST-generated soot particles, and the measurement of sub-23 nm particles emitted by a diesel engine. The high stability of the DR in combination with >99% volatile particle removal and a cutoff size (d_{50}) at 7.5 nm suggest that the SCPS may deliver solid emitted particles for robust particle number measurements down to at least 10 nm.

Introduction

Ultrafine particles with sizes less than 100 nm are considered a severe health risk causing cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases as well as lung cancer and are associated with millions of deaths per year [1]. EU is traditionally leading the efforts towards the reduction of vehicle particle emissions imposing limits to particle mass emissions, since 1992 and particle number emissions, since 2011, from internal combustion powered vehicles. The current emission limits in Europe concern Diesel and Gasoline Direct Injection (GDI) vehicles and are set at 6×10^{11} #/km as measured under the World-harmonized Light duty Transient Cycle, WLTC for the light-duty vehicles. In the US only the particle mass emissions are regulated while China's latest regulation follows the European one and will

also concern Port Fuel Injection (PFI) vehicles. EU also sets limits for Diesel and GDI vehicle Real Driving Emissions (RDE), currently being $1.5 \times (=9 \times 10^{11}$ #/km) as measured by Portable Emissions Measurement Systems.

The value of #/km for each type of vehicle is measured for the WLTC on chassis dynamometer following the Particle Measurement Programme (PMP) protocol as suggested by the PMP group. Only solid particles are taken into account. Under the PMP, the entire exhaust is transferred into a dilution tunnel where it is diluted with fresh filtered air (Constant Volume Sampling, CVS) [2]. The measuring instruments are sampling through the CVS through a Volatile Particle Removal (VPR) system, consisting of two dilution stages (one hot and one cold) and an Evaporation Tube (ET) in between operating at 300-400 °C for the removal of volatiles. The measuring instrument is usually an optical counter like the Condensation Particle Counter (CPC) which measures particles down to 23 nm. The CPC should have at least 50% measuring efficiency for 23 nm particles. On the other hand, the RDE measurements are performed obviously without the use of the CVS, and the VPR is connected directly to the tailpipe.

The 23 nm cut-off in the measurements was mainly due to the technological limitations in the sampling of smaller particles rather than any other reason. The uncertainties in the measurement of sub-23 nm particles could jeopardize the validity of the total particle measurements and come from the probable inability of the evaporation tube and the rest of the system to treat those ultra-fine particles, usually of high volatile nature without the production of significant artifacts. Nevertheless, the 23nm cut-off did not bring any significant errors in the measurement of Diesel engine exhaust particulates as Diesel engines, in most of the cases, tend to emit particles of larger sizes and indeed larger than 23 nm. However, nowadays GDIs constitute the majority in the new gasoline vehicle sales as this technology offers significant fuel economy with respect to PFIs. The very fast fuel/air mixture preparation and the cylinder wall wetting due to the direct injection of fuel can lead to local fuel-rich areas and the formation of soot particles. GDI soot particle emissions are characterized by smaller than the Diesel particles and the high aromatic content of soot (more "wet" soot). Number-based particle emissions from GDIs are higher than the emissions from Diesel with DPF and in many cases will overwhelm the 6×10^{11} #/km limit [3]. Additionally, the fleet is moving to more highly boosted GDI engines which has been shown to emit smaller particles than unboosted [4]. As GDI particles are smaller in size than Diesel with concentration peaks in the range of 10-60 nm, a particular portion of the total particles are particles with sizes < 23 nm. Usually, 20-50 % of total GDI particles are below 23nm, and these are not considered by the current regulation [5,6]. Moreover, the higher aromatic content

of the GDI particles leads to significant secondary aerosol formation multiplying the associated health risk. Due to the above-described reasons the 23 nm threshold will be most probably decreased to 10 nm by the European regulation in the very near future.

The process of establishing the new particle emission regulations down to 10 nm necessitates the evaluation of the capability of the current measurement protocols for efficient sampling of the particles of the respective size-range. Most uncertainties concern the ET as well as the comparison between the CVS and the tailpipe measurements. As RDE measurements can only be accomplished in the tailpipe, it would be ideal that both chassis and RDE homologation tests to be done in the tailpipe. CVS and tailpipe measurements, in general, correlate well with small differences (<15%). However, particle agglomeration, diffusion and thermophoresis in the transfer line between the exhaust and the CVS tunnel can result in significant particle losses (estimated theoretically to be circa 17%) [7]. On top of that, there is much uncertainty resulting from errors in exhaust flow determination and discrepancies in the time alignment among the different signals from the measurement analyzers and the exhaust flow sensors due to the large tunnels needed. On the other hand, tailpipe measurements suffer from inaccuracies in the dilution factor estimation due to the fast pressure and temperature fluctuations in the exhaust.

With respect to the ET efficiency, alternative technologies have been proposed. One technique with high potential is considered to be the Catalytic Stripper (CS). In this case, instead of a simple heated tube, a catalyst coated monolith is used, also operating in high temperature (200-400 C) and able to oxidize the volatile fraction of the soot particles. SUREAL-23 is an EU funded project with one of its primary targets being the design and the realization of an effective and accurate sampling and conditioning system for the precise measurement of particle emissions down to 10nm [8]. In this work, we will present the development of our optimized Sampling and Conditioning Particle System (SCPS) for tailpipe measurements able to accurately fix the dilution ratio at the desired level and also comprising an innovative CS.

Experimental

General instrument description

The SCPS is a two-stage diluter, designed to minimize particle losses, especially in the sub-23 nm region. The first stage is a porous tube diluter, positioned just after the sampling probe. This type of dilution minimizes diffusion particle losses, which is critical for sampling and measuring sub-23 nm particles [9]. The second stage is an “ejector” type diluter, based on a prototype dilution system developed by JRC [11]. This type of a diluter creates vacuum by accelerating compressed air through an orifice, thus exhaust gas sample is drawn into the SCPS. Between the two stages, a catalytic stripper is fitted, in order to remove volatiles. The catalytic stripper was developed specially for the SCPS and is further presented in the following

section. Figure 1 illustrates the concept of SCPS.

Figure 1. The SCPS: 1: Sampling probe, 2: Porous tube diluter (1st stage), 3: Catalytic Stripper, 4: Ejector type diluter (2nd stage), 5: Diffuser

Two sensors, able to measure temperature and pressure, are connected to the sampling probe, at the tip of the inlet tube, in order to monitor continually the conditions in the exhaust tube.

The dilution air in the first stage must be heated, to avoid particle condensation. The porous tube diluter is placed inside a tube that can be supplied with hot air or water to keep at a constant temperature to prevent any cold spots. The following stage can also be heated externally, by an electric resistance, to bring the catalytic stripper to proper working temperature. Since condensation of the gas sample is eliminated by the first dilution stage, the dilution air at the second stage is not required to be hot, and the ejector diluter is therefore not heated. The final part of the SCPS is a diffuser, where gas velocity is reduced, downstream of the ejector orifice.

Catalytic stripper

Solid particle number measurements necessitate an aerosol conditioning system that removes volatile particles and does not create artifacts. For this scope, SCPS employs a catalytic stripper specially designed to handle high aerosol flows. The catalytic stripper is composed of a cylindrical honeycomb flow-through cordierite monolith (Length: 50 mm, Diameter: 24.5 mm, cell density: 200 cpsi) placed in a stainless-steel canister. The main novelty we introduce is the use of a dual function monolith acting both as an oxidation catalyst and a sulphur trap instead of two monolithic reactors. The dual function of the monolith offers a compact structure that prevents any flow instabilities that may increase particle losses. In our configuration, the flow first passes through the oxidation catalyst that is coated with Pt and subsequently through the sulphur-trap which is coated with a Ce/Zr mixed oxide. An analytical description of the catalytic stripper's development and performance can be found in [12]. In summary, the catalytic stripper, that operates at 400°C wall temperature, was found to fully oxidize (>99%) tetracontane particles with mean diameter 30 nm for flows up to 25 l/min that correspond to 79,600 GHSV. The maximum sulphur storage capacity, tested with SO₂, was found to be 7.3 mg of S for complete (>99.9%) SO₂ removal efficiency. After its saturation, the CS may be regenerated maintaining the 60-70% of the initial sulphur capacity while the tetracontane oxidation efficiency is not influenced. Solid particle penetration down to 10 nm is higher than 80% offering the possibility to perform sub-23 nm solid particle measurements without significant size-dependent particle losses.

Results

DR calculation accuracy

The dilution ratio (DR) calculation is defined in Eq.1. The sample (Q_s) and dilution air (Q_{da}) flowrates refer to standard conditions (21.1 °C and 101.3mbar).

$$DR = \frac{Q_s + Q_{da}}{Q_s} \quad (1)$$

The total dilution air, introduced in the porous tube and the ejector diluter, is known and measured continuously by means of mass flowmeters. The sample flow is calculated, based on pressure drop measurement across an orifice, which is located in the sampling tube where the sample flow is introduced. It is well known theoretically from Bernoulli's equation, that the volumetric flow rate is proportional to the square root of the DP generated by an orifice and the density of the gas.

The calibration of the orifice at atmospheric air and normal conditions can be seen in Figure 2. The sample flow was measured with a TSI mass flow meter (model 4140, range 0-20Nlpm). The relationship of the sample flow Q_s with the square root of the DP across the orifice follows an almost linear relationship ($R^2=0.986$). Therefore, the sample flow can be accurately calculated by the precise measurement of the DP.

Figure 2. Orifice calibration for sample flow calculation.

Local pressure and temperature variations, normally met in the exhaust gas environment, change the gas density and compensation is needed so that DP only responds to changes in flow. Pressure and temperature compensation correct the measured DP at actual operating conditions to an equivalent DP at calibration conditions.

The DR calculation accuracy of the instrument was tested in steady-state diesel exhaust by comparing with DR calculated with CO_2 gas concentration (Eq. 2),

$$DR_{CO_2} = \frac{CO_{2s} - CO_{2da}}{CO_{2out} - CO_{2da}}, \quad (2)$$

where CO_{2s} is the raw, CO_{2da} is the dilution air and CO_{2out} is the diluted CO_2 concentration.

The test consisted of 20 trials, in which both the engine and the instrument control parameters varied, such as to include a vast range of operation which would be met at current transient cycles. Figure 3 plots the calculated and experimentally determined dilution ratio

against the different operation points. The agreement is satisfactory, with a maximum deviation of 6%.

Figure 3. DR calculated by the algorithm in comparison with CO_2 measured in steady-state engine points.

DR stability at transient conditions

The stability of the DR was tested on the exhaust of a gasoline vehicle running the WLTC on a chassis dynamometer. The SCPS sampled at the tailpipe, and the DR value was set at 28.5. A coefficient of variation $CoV=0.103$ was achieved throughout the cycle. It should be noted, that DR variation, at a certain degree, in transient conditions, is unavoidable as fluctuations of the temperature, and thus density, of the sample gas results in the variation in the calculation of the sample flow rate.

Figure 4. DR stability at a WLTC cycle.

Accurate real-time calculation of the DR through differential pressure measurement eliminates the need of CO_2 gas DR measurement, which is associated with unreliable measurements due to engine fuel cut-off, transfer line hysteresis and analyzer response issues at transients.

Volatile particle removal efficiency

According to the PMP protocol, VPR systems should be able to remove tetracontane particles with $D_m \geq 30$ nm, and number concentration $>10^4$ #/cm³ with efficiency higher than 99% as this challenge aerosol is considered to represent the hydrocarbon portion of exhaust [13]. The tetracontane removal efficiency decreases with increasing particle size, number concentration, and lower residence

time in the VPR [14]. The inclusion of sub-23 nm particles in the legislation may result in stricter limits for the tetracontane removal [7].

Here, we test the volatile removal efficiency of the SCPS with polydisperse tetracontane particles with mean diameter $D_m \sim 30$ nm. This test is more representative of the real world, and more demanding than the monodisperse tetracontane removal test as the number concentration is higher, and the tetracontane particle size varies from 10 to 70 nm. Figure 5 shows the tetracontane removal efficiency testing apparatus. Accordingly, tetracontane particles were generated with a volatile particle generator (VPG) based on the evaporation/condensation technique. VPG is capable of providing tetracontane particles with variable size and number concentration as well as aerosol flows up to 30 (l/min). The analytic description of the VPG can be found in [12]. Followingly, the aerosol flow was driven either to an SMPS to measure the original particle size distribution or to the SCPS and then to the SMPS. The SMPS consisted of a nano-DMA (TSI, 3085) and a CPC with cut-off size 2.5 nm (TSI, 3776).

Figure 5. Experimental setup used for testing the removal efficiency of tetracontane particles.

The SCPS volatile removal efficiency was tested at six different operating conditions presented in Table 1. The parameters that varied were the total flow passing through the porous diluter and thus through the catalytic stripper, the temperature of the porous heater, and the ejector flow. For each set point, the dilution ratio differs and takes values in the range 30 to 57.

Table 1. The SCPS operation conditions during the volatile removal efficiency testing.

Set Point	Porous flow (lpm)	Porous heater (°C)	Ejector flow (lpm)	Dilution Ratio
A	23	300	70	40
B	23	350	70	40
C	30	300	70	47
D	12	300	70	30
E	35	300	70	57
F	20	300	120	38

The tetracontane particle size distribution that passed through the SCPS was stable through all tests, and it had a mean mobility diameter $D_m = 29$ nm and total number concentration 7.1×10^6 (#/cm³). The number concentration of particles with $D_m \geq 30$ nm was 3×10^6 (#/cm³), much higher than the PMP protocol demands. Figure 6 plots the upstream tetracontane particle size distribution (challenge aerosol) as well as downstream the SCPS at the different operation set points. The size distributions are corrected for the dilution ratio. We note that no tetracontane particles are detected downstream the SCPS. Specifically, the removal efficiency for $D_m \geq 10$ nm is higher than 99.9% for all set points. Thus, SCPS is able to completely remove high concentrations of tetracontane particles with a diameter larger than 30 nm.

Figure 6. The tetracontane particle size distribution upstream (challenge aerosol) and downstream the SCPS for six different operation set points.

Solid particle penetration efficiency

Ultrafine particle losses in the SCPS mainly occur due to thermophoresis and diffusion. Thermophoretic losses depend on the temperature difference between the aerosol flow and the wall; aerosol particle motion is always in the direction of decreasing temperature [16]. According to a recent study [17] highly polydisperse fractal-like agglomerates may exhibit a size-dependent thermophoresis due to the effect of the monomer shielding within an agglomerate [18]. However, this is not the case for automotive applications [19], and thermophoresis may be considered to depend slightly on particle size. In contrary, diffusion losses are size-dependent and become important for particles with smaller mobility diameter, D_m ; the diameter of a virtual sphere of the same average mobility (friction coefficient) as the particle under the same momentum transfer flow conditions [20, 21]. Besides the particle size, also the flow rate and the tube length are important for diffusion losses [22].

The size-specific penetration fraction, P_i , is defined as the ratio of the number concentration of particles with size i at the outlet, N_{out} , to the inlet, N_{in} , of the SCPS,

$$P_i = \frac{N_{out}}{N_{in}} \quad (1)$$

In this study, we employed the combustion aerosol standard (CAST) to generate solid ultrafine particles. CAST produces soot particles in a co-flow diffusion flame of propane (C_3H_8) where the combustion air is coaxially supplied. Subsequently, soot particles are mixed with a quenching nitrogen flow to stabilize them and prevent any further combustion processes. recent studies have shown that under specific operating conditions, like fuel mix with nitrogen, it may produce a large fraction of semi-volatile material while the black fraction reduces [12, 23, 24]. At small particle sizes, CAST-generated particles may be either volatile or solid immature soot particles with condensed organic species. In order to ensure that the CAST-generated particles were solid and thermally stable the CAST generator was followed by volatile removal setup, based on an oxidation catalyst that operated at 450°C and a hot dilution and cold dilution stages performed with ejector diluters (DEKATI, DI-1000) upstream and downstream the oxidation catalyst, respectively.

We used three CAST set points (SPx) to determine the particle penetration through the SCPS; SP80, SP40, and SP20. The number x indicates the mean mobility diameter which, however, downstream the oxidation catalyst reduces. Table 2 summarizes the operating conditions of CAST at different set points.

Table 2. The operating conditions of CAST generator

Set Point	C3H8 (l/min)	Quench gas N2 (l/min)	Mixing gas N2 (l/min)	Oxidation air O2/N2
SP80	0.058	7.5	0.29	1.48
SP40	0.06	7.5	0.29	1.3
SP20	0.06	7.5	0.38	1.3

We determined the size-specific penetration fraction using two different experimental setups presented in Figure 7; setup A for monodisperse particles and setup B for polydisperse particles. Measurements with polydisperse particles are not as precise as with monodisperse particles may give an approximate penetration fraction for more sizes. In setup A, the particle size selection was done with a long-DMA (TSI, 3081) for sizes $D_m=[100, 50, 30]$ nm and a nano-DMA (TSI, 3085) for sizes $D_m=[15, 10, 7.5]$ nm. The sheath to aerosol was 1.5:15. The number concentration was measured with a CPC (TSI, 3776). In setup B, all particle sizes generated by CAST were driven either through the SCPS and then to an SMPS or directly to an SMPS. The SMPS consisted of a long-DMA (3081) for SP80 and SP40 and a nano-DMA (TSI, 3085) for SP20, and of a CPC (TSI, 3776).

Figure 7. Experimental setup employed for measuring the solid particle penetration through the SCPS.

The SCPS operated at four different set points. Table 3 lists the operating conditions. The dilution ratio varied in the range 31-59.

Table 3. The SCPS operation conditions during the solid particle penetration testing.

Set Point	Porous flow (lpm)	Porous heater (°C)	Ejector flow (lpm)	Dilution Ratio
G	10	300	50	31
H	10	300	120	33
I	35	300	120	50
J	35	300	50	59

Figure 8 plots the size-specific penetration fraction, P_i , against the mobility diameter, D_m , and the standard deviation of the measurements with monodisperse particles. The penetration fraction of monodisperse particles is calculated comparing the CPC number concentration measurements upstream and downstream the SCPS while for polydisperse particles it is calculated comparing the size distributions upstream and downstream the SCPS. For polydisperse particles we plot only particle sizes where the number concentration is at least half of the maximum size-specific number concentration. This arbitrarily chosen constraint ensures that the statistic sample is adequate. Our results were averaged over three measurements for each CAST set point over all SCPS operation set points.

Figure 8. Solid particle penetration fraction against the particle's mobility diameter determined with polydisperse CAST-generated particles.

Measurements performed with monodisperse and polydisperse particles are in excellent agreement with the maximum difference being 6%. We note that the penetration fraction is almost stable and, thus, size-independent in the size range from 100 nm down to ~17 nm. For sizes smaller than 17 nm the P_i decreases due to diffusion losses but still remains high. The cut-off size D_{50} , the size where half of the particles pass through the SCPS, cannot be specified with monodisperse particles measurements as even down to $D_m=7.5$ nm the penetration fraction is 0.59. For polydisperse particles the cut-off size is found to be $D_{50}=7.3$ nm. We didn't manage to produce high number concentrations of particles smaller than 7.3 nm.

According to the PMP protocol solid particle number measurements are corrected with an average particle number concentration reduction factor, $PCRF_{av}$. $PCRF_{av}$ equals the inverse mean penetration fraction, $PCRF_{av}=1/P_{av}$. Currently, the $PCRF_{av}$ is calculated with the size specific PCRF of particles with mobility diameter 100 nm ($PCRF_{100}$), 50 nm ($PCRF_{50}$), and 30 nm ($PCRF_{30}$) [15]. Moreover, there are limits for the ratios $PCRF_{100}/PCRF_{50}<1.2$ and $PCRF_{100}/PCRF_{30}<1.3$. PCRF ratio limits guarantee that measurement uncertainty due to size-dependent particle losses is low.

Particle number measurements with cut-off size below the current 23 nm limit require the addition of lower sizes at the average penetration fraction calculation. Herein, and in agreement with previous studies that investigate solid particle number down to 10 nm [15], we propose the inclusion of particles with $D_m=15$ nm ($PCRF_{15}$).

$$PCRF_{av} = \frac{PCRF_{100} + PCRF_{50} + PCRF_{30} + PCRF_{15}}{4} \quad (4)$$

Accordingly, Table 4 presents the size specific penetration fraction, the average penetration fraction and the respective standard deviation as well as the ratio between the penetration fractions determined with monodisperse particles. We observe that PCRF remains stable for $D_m=100, 50,$ and 30 nm. For $D_m=15$ nm the PCRF increases but the ratio $PCRF_{15}/PCRF_{100}$ is very low and, therefore, measurement uncertainties that occur when particle losses depend strongly on size are minimized. The average particle concentration reduction factor for measurements down to 10 nm is $PCRF_{av}=1.19\pm 8\%$.

Table 4. The Particle Concentration Reduction Factor (PCRF) of the SCPS.

D_m (nm)	PCRF _i	PCRF _i /PCRF ₁₀₀
100	1.15	
50	1.16	1.01
30	1.13	0.98
15	1.34	1.16
Average	1.19±8%	

We further investigated the possibility to use a unique correction factor to predict the original number concentration of different size distributions generated by CAST. The CAST set points we used were SP80, SP40, and SP20 that had mean mobility diameter 70 nm, 25 nm, and 10 nm. The experimental setup was presented in Figure 7 (Setup B). Figure 9 plots the CAST size distribution at the inlet of SCPS and compares it to the size distribution downstream the SCPS for set point G. As expected, we note that the number concentration decreases downstream the SCPS. For smaller particles this decrease is even higher. For SP80 and SP40 the total number concentration decreases 9.5%, 16.4%, respectively, while for SP20 the decrease is 40.2%. The mean diameter remains the same for SP80 and SP40 while for SP20 it increases 6% showing that the particle losses are size dependent. A similar behavior was observed also for the other three SCPS set points; H, I, J. We also applied the $PCRF_{av}=1.19$ presented in Table 4 to correct the particle size distributions presented in Figure 9. For SP80 and SP40 we predict very well the inlet number concentration. Specifically, we slightly overestimate it for the SP80 (7% difference) while for SP40 the agreement is excellent (<1% difference). For SP20 even after the correction we underestimate the number concentration. This is an extreme case where the sub-10 nm number concentration is half of the total. If we consider only particles $D_m > 10$ nm then the difference between the original number concentration and the predicted is ~18%.

Figure 9. The particle size distribution of CAST-generated particles at set points SP80, SP40, and SP20 upstream and downstream the SCPS as well as corrected particle size distributions with the PCRF.

Sub-23 nm particles emission measurement

The feasibility of the SCPS to measure solid particles in the sub-23 nm region was investigated in the diesel engine exhaust. The single-cylinder engine (Hatz 1B-30) used, was operated at a steady-state point, 3000rpm and partial load, and the SCPS sampled from raw exhaust without an aftertreatment system. The sub-23nm particles were produced by combustion of a mixture of fuel with Ce-based fuel additive (Envirox™ DPF assist-Energenics Europe Ltd). These kind of fuel additives are commercially available and sold with the

purpose of assisting the regeneration of the DPF. Elemental analysis of the additive with inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) method, focusing on the Ce concentration, revealed 17000ppm of Ce. In order to produce a sufficient number of particles, the additive dose exceeded the manufacturer's specifications. The particle number distribution was measured at the outlet of the SCPS with a standard SMPS system. Results are shown in Fig. 10. The first peak of the bimodal particle size distribution, around $D_m=13$ nm, is attributed to the Ce particles. The second peak, in the region of $D_m=70$ nm, is typical accumulation mode particles of diesel combustion.

Figure 10. Solid sub-23nm particle measurement with SMPS at the outlet of the SCPS.

Summary/Conclusions

In this work, we have presented an advancement to the PMP technology able to efficiently sample and condition engine exhaust for the precise measurement of solid particle emissions down to 10 nm. The presented SCPS is a partial exhaust sampler and does not rely on the CVS providing more compatible with RDE-PEMS results. However, it also provides a stable DR, and it calculates the DR values very accurately, in real-time without the need for CO₂ analyzers. Hydrocarbons and sulphur are very efficiently removed while the particle losses are kept to minimal values, well beyond other state-of-the-art devices, even for sub-23 nm particles. The developed SCPS will enable the update of future particle emissions regulations to also account for particles down to 10nm as well as will ensure measurements closer to real-world emissions.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

CAST	Combustion Aerosol Standard
CPC	Condensation Particle Counter
CS	Catalytic Stripper
CVS	Constant Volume Sampling
DMA	Differential Mobility Analyzer
DPF	Diesel Particulate Filter
DR	Dilution Ratio
ET	Evaporation Tube
EU	European Union
GDI	Gasoline Direct Injection
ICP-OES	inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry
PCRF	Particle Correction Reduction Factor
PFI	Port Fuel Injection
RDE	Real Driving Emissions
SMPS	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
SCPS	Sampling and Conditioning Particle System
WLTC	World-harmonized Light-duty Transient Cycle